

Financial Performance, Market Efficiency, and Stock Price Predictability in Nepal's Banking Sector During and After COVID-19

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Abstract

We investigate the empirical relationship between key financial indicators and the market price of listed banks in Nepal, using a panel dataset comprising quarterly observations from 12 banks covering the period 2020 to 2024. The core objective is to identify the most significant determinants of share price among variables such as Earnings Per Share (EPS), Price-to-Earnings (P/E) Ratio, Loan-to-Deposit (LD) Ratio, Non-Performing Loans (NPL), and Net Worth Per Share (NWPS). Employing the Fixed Effects Model (FEM), selected based on the Breusch-Pagan LM and Hausman tests, the study ensures robust estimation by accounting for heterogeneity across banks. The panel regression results highlight that EPS has a statistically significant and positive influence on share price ($\beta = 10.08$, $p < 0.01$), underscoring the critical role of profitability in investor valuation decisions. In contrast, other variables such as the P/E Ratio, LD Ratio, NPL, and NWPS exhibit theoretically expected signs but lack statistical significance. This may reflect the presence of behavioural biases, market inefficiencies, and structural challenges in the Nepalese stock market. The overall model demonstrates moderate explanatory power, with an R^2 of 0.518, and is statistically significant ($F = 11.71$, $p < 0.01$). The findings emphasize the importance of profitability metrics like EPS in influencing investor behaviour. The study recommends improved financial disclosures, regulatory reforms, and enhanced investor education to promote a more efficient and transparent capital market in Nepal.

Keywords: *banking sector; fixed effects model, Nepal stock market, panel data, share price*